

Electricity Treasure Hunt

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INTRODUCTION

The project is developed during this spring semester 2012 in the course 'Holistic design of systems'. We have been working with the electric energy system in relation to private consumption. The problem is that the private consumer has an estimated overconsumption by 10% of electricity. By gaining awareness of own electricity consumption, the private consumer can reduce their electricity consumption with 10% without compromising their current life style. Based on this knowledge, the research question of this project has been: *How can household consumption of electricity be visualised, realised and possibly changed by engaging the public with information and activities?*

The developed concept solving this is the 'Electricity Treasure Hunt'. The target group is private consumers, e.g. a family, single person etc.

ELECTRICITY TREASURE HUNT

The goal of the Electricity Treasure Hunt is twofold. The Treasure Hunt should create *awareness* on the private electricity consumption as well as *maintenance* support of the gained awareness. The different steps in the Electricity Treasure Hunt concept are shown below:

Figure 1 The activities in the concept

A physical treasure hunt with free access is placed in the public area. The treasure hunt consists of five interactive installations there should be engaging, explorative, reflective to own household and fun to experience. The participant gain awareness and knowledge of the system of practices around electricity consumption in the household. The challenge has been to link the gained awareness to the actual household. After finishing the physical treasure hunt, the participant(s) can borrow a "sparometer". They can map the electricity consumption of each product in the household. To support this measuring at home, a virtual supporting platform is included in the concept. Research shows that this will reduce the electricity consumption with 10%. The documentation of 10% reduction is a crucial point when it comes to the business plan, there are based on founding's, partnerships with electric companies, and sponsorships from other interests.